
DEPICTION OF CLIMATIC CONCERNS IN “NEW YORK 2140” BY KIM STANLEY ROBINSON

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Annotation: The growth of the climate novel is testimony to climate change increasingly entering the public consciousness. The novel *New York 2140* by Kim Stanley Robinson is one of the best novels of this kind and it brilliantly depicts the theme of climate concerns as a consequence of human activities on the environment over a long period of time.

Key words: cli-fi, climate novel, environmental issues, global warming.

This paper examines how climatic concerns are fictionally expressed in the novel *New York 2140* by an American sci-fi author Kim Stanley Robinson. He is also a well-established, professional cli-fi author whose works are at the core of the climate fiction genre. The plot of this novel is set in New York City a few hundred years from now and explores a wide range of topics and themes in relation to climate change. The city, which is nicknamed Super Venice, has been altered by climate change and sees that streets have been replaced by canals, airplanes are replaced by lighter-than-air airships and skyscrapers have become islands, amongst others. The novel, nonetheless explores how humans juggle through and adopt within this new world brought upon them.

The climate change in this novel is depicted as a consequence of human activities against nature. Right from the beginning of the novel, there is a glimpse of climatic concerns as Jeff tells Mutt that they are “in a mass extinction event, sea level rise, climate change,…” [4, p. 12]. Manhattan is flooded and looks like a majestic “super-Venice” [4, p. 14]. The rise in sea water levels has inundated New York City

as well as all the coastal cities worldwide, and this came about when the “ice monster melted ten thousand years ago, sea level rose about three hundred feet”, subsequently inundating all the world’s coastal towns [4, p. 42]. Furthermore, the two big surges that swamped the coastal cities in the world called ‘The Pulses’ were each a “complete psychodrama decade, a meltdown in history, a breakdown in society, a refugee nightmare, an eco-catastrophe, the planet gone collectively nuts” [4, p. 44], and according to The Citizen character, they were the “first-order catastrophe” in the world to bring much destruction to the environment [4, p. 153]. The Citizen further claims that the First Pulse came as extreme shock to people, however the second one not. The Citizen elucidates that people’s profound ignorance for the ramifications of “their carbon burn” had “unleashed the ice” resulting in sea water levels rising, which severely damaged the “global distribution system”, and caused a “depression that was even more damaging to the people of that generation than the accompanying refugee crisis, which, using the unit popular at the time, was rated as fifty katrinas” [4, p. 153]. That period was quite bad, however the extreme disruption of world trade was far worse as far as business was concerned because it came with a lot of economic challenges to the world which led to and intensified capitalism worldwide, which is in conjunction with Gardiner (2020) who asserts that threats such as climate change can disrupt the world economies, just as it is happening in New York 2140 (2017).

Moreover, in the 2060s, a volcanic eruption was mimicked by tossing a “few billion tons of sulfur dioxide” in the atmosphere in order to “deflect a fair bit of sunlight, depressing temperatures for a decade or two”, nevertheless it was not adequate to “halt the warming” [4, p. 154]. That was because the “pertinent heat was already deep in the oceans, and it was not going anywhere anytime soon, no matter how people played with the global thermos at imagining they had godlike powers” [4, p. 154]. It is, therefore “that ocean heat” that triggered the First Pulse to ‘pulse’, and later caused the Second Pulse [4, 154]. In conjunction, according to the ecocriticism theory as asserted by DeMott (2018), climate change did not just appear from nowhere nor through invisible causes, but as a result of several events and activities concerning human beings’ dealings with nature. In this regard, the present researcher,

therefore similarly argues that, even with the possible changes that man made after observing and experiencing the effects of an altered climate, these were still not sufficient to put an end to these effects that were in place. This is also endorsed by El-Alshry (2009) who affirms that though numerous contingency plans to mitigate the effects of an altered climate, they could potentially never suffice to diminish further greenhouse gas emissions.

Additionally, The Citizen asserts that sometimes people claim to not have anticipated the Second Pulse, but he contends that “they did” know that it was coming [4, p. 154]. The Citizen argues that they knew, because the people “played with the global thermostat imagining they had godlike powers”, but they did not [4, p. 154]. This proves that though humans might be aware of their actions which could result in an altered climate, the consequences thereof might not sink in until it is almost too late to do anything about the phenomenon. Similarly, Gardiner (2020) asserts that warnings about climate change have been issued for several years, however certain people, especially political figures tend to ignore these, and these threats could be avoided or at the bare minimum, eased if earlier actions towards these forewarnings were reckoned with.

Correspondingly, The Citizen maintains that people knew that the Second Pulse was coming, because they have “published their papers, and shouted and waved their arms” in relation to the changing climate and a few “canny and deeply thoughtful sci-fi writers” have brilliantly depicted “such an eventuality” in their writings, yet everybody else ignored these and went on “torching” the earth like a “Burning Man pyromasterpiece” [4, p. 154]. Furthermore, The Citizen asserts that that is how much these “knuckleheads cared about their grandchildren, and that’s how much they believed their scientists, even though every time they felt a slight cold coming on they ran to the nearest scientist (i.e. doctor) to seek aid” [4, 154]. The present researcher postulates that, having read the published papers and broadcasted news on climate change, people are ought to make great modifications to aid in slowing down global warming, and even though the results of this phenomenon is not immediate, it could affect the next generations more than those who are actually currently

contributing to this phenomenon. This is in line with Trexler (2015) who posit that the damage caused to the environment might be irreversible, however if climate change is humanised through narratives, it could serve as alarm bell to humans and reconsider how to live. Additionally, Watts (2018) posits that this global phenomenon should be approached intergenerationally, and through multiple perspectives, thus the present researcher believes that it is could be up to the current generation to make sure that the environment is well taken care off for future generations, because as earlier stated by Trexler (2015), these damages might be irreversible and they could affect the future generations more than they are affecting the current generation.

To conclude the analysis of New York 2140 (2017), the affiliation of man and nature in this novel is in full swing that the two are connected and interrelated, and every change that the environment goes through, it will one way or another affect human beings as it is depicted in the novel. Similarly, environmental degradation is mostly as a result of human beings’ actions, and this has several consequences such as displacement, migration, food shortages, amongst others, as asserted by several scholars, just as it is portrayed in the novel.

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